

The Biden Legacy in the Middle East

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In January 2020, President Joe Biden succeeded Donald Trump, one of the most controversial presidents in U.S. history. The bar, in short, was low. Biden's main asset, at first, was simply that he was not Donald Trump. This echoed an earlier transition when Barack Obama succeeded George W. Bush, the architect of the disastrous 2003 US invasion of Iraq. Obama had barely been in office before receiving the Nobel Peace Prize, signaling mainly international hopes for his administration and relief that the Bush days were over. That same sense seemed to accompany Biden at first, and for good reason. Trump's first administration seemed to be a source of constant chaos, while Biden was widely perceived as a calming influence, as stabilizing the US role in the world, and essentially as an adult having finally entered the room.

At first, these expectations seemed warranted. Trump had presided over a weakening economy and chose to deal with a catastrophic healthcare crisis – the global COVID pandemic – as some kind of partisan affair best handled as though it was a reality TV event. Biden, in contrast, showed something that Trump never had: empathy. Biden's administration then presided over the most successful vaccine rollout and distribution system in US history, and openly talked about helping the country to heal. It is not surprising, therefore, that many expected similar depths

of empathy regarding US policy toward the Middle East, only to be deeply disappointed, to put it mildly.

In the Middle East, Trump largely ignored some longstanding regional allies, like Jordan, in favor of a de facto close alignment with the regimes in Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, and Israel. He seemed to handle US Middle East policy as a personal affair between rulers and openly disdained regional expertise. Trump's other policies in the Middle East included ending the US role in the Joint Comprehensive Plan for Action (JCPOA -- the multilateral nuclear arms deal with Iran), cutting off US aid to UNRWA (the main aid organization supporting Palestinian refugees), while also moving the US embassy in Israel from Tel Aviv to Jerusalem, and recognizing the longstanding Israeli annexation of the Golan Heights. Trump also claimed credit for a series of normalization agreements between Israel and Bahrain, the UAE, Morocco, and Sudan – known as the Abraham Accords. Upon taking office, Biden maintained most of these policies, but he did attempt – unsuccessfully – to revive some sort of arms deal with Iran, while restoring funding to UNRWA. Although Biden, too, would later halt US aid to UNRWA following the October 2023 Hamas attack on Israel.

The gap between the Trump and Biden foreign policies was perhaps more pronounced outside the region, as Trump had derided major institutions and alliances from the United Nations to NATO, and had withdrawn the US from the Paris Accords on climate change. Biden, in contrast, saw US power and influence as predicated on a multilateral coalition of Western democracies, and hence restored support to the UN, NATO, and other regional and global institutions, while also re-joining the global treaty to address climate change. This is especially important because Biden's major departures from the Trump years were based on deep beliefs in multilateralism, institutional cooperation, and, above all, a commitment to global norms – at least as these were defined by the dominant Western powers in the international system. Yet here, too, the Middle East didn't seem to be included. While Biden restored and repaired damaged alliances across Europe and North America, his administration failed dramatically when it came to these same “shared norms” in the Middle East.

As the Israel-Hamas war dragged on for months, and then well over a year, the death toll was staggering and appalling, and the continuing U.S. rhetoric about global norms, the rule of law, and international human rights seemed that much more jarring and tone-deaf given the humanitarian disaster that was unfolding in Gaza. To say that the Gaza catastrophe tarnished the Biden legacy would be a profound understatement. It seemed to contradict everything the administration claimed to stand for, and it may even have cost Biden's designated successor, Vice President Kamala Harris, the 2024 election.

In a farewell speech, Biden harped on many successes – record improvements in increased levels of employment, a revived

economy, and bipartisan legislation to invest in infrastructure projects in all 50 US states. He defended his administration's extensive support for Ukraine in its war with Russia. Perhaps that should have been the start of a positive presidential legacy. But Biden also unwittingly seemed to have paved the way for the return of Trump, who immediately took a hammer to almost every Biden domestic or foreign policy, to US democratic and legal institutions, and to regional and global organizations. Rather jarringly, Trump seemed determined to undermine US allies especially, stoking diplomatic crises and trade wars with Canada, Mexico, and even Denmark (as the US president demanded that it hand over Greenland).

In his first few weeks, however, Trump turned to Gaza. In January 2025, Hamas and Israel had finally agreed to a fragile ceasefire. Both Biden and Trump claimed credit for the temporary respite. But there was little to celebrate. Gaza lay largely in ruins. More than 50,000 people had been killed in Israeli bombing, the overwhelming majority innocent civilians.

Biden was supposed to be “not Trump” and mark the end of the Trump years as the bridge to a new era at home and abroad. Instead, the Biden legacy turned out to be a mere interregnum between the first and second Trump administrations, with the latter having none of the (admittedly few) guard rails that may have slightly reined in the first. It thus overshadowed any of the positives, in both domestic and international policy, that Biden felt should be his legacy. And for the Middle East, the legacy seemed to be forever dominated by Gaza, even as further disaster continued to unfold. ♦